

2 Layered double hydroxides as slow-release fertilizer
3 compounds for the micronutrient molybdenum

4 Maarten Everaert^{†*}, Erik Smolder[†], Mike J. McLaughlin[‡], Ivan Andelkovic[‡], Simon Smolders[§],
5 Fien Degryse[‡]

6 [†] Division of Soil and Water Management, Department of Earth and Environmental Science, KU Leuven,
7 Kasteelpark Arenberg 20, B-3001 Heverlee, Belgium.

8 [‡] School of Agriculture, Food and Wine, The University of Adelaide, PMB 1, Waite Campus, Glen
9 Osmond, SA 5064, Australia.

10 [§] Centre for Membrane Separations, Adsorption, Catalysis and Spectroscopy for Sustainable Solutions
11 (cMACS), KU Leuven, Celestijnenlaan 200F, 3001 Leuven, Belgium.

12 * Corresponding author: maarten.everaert@kuleuven.be

13 ORCID ID:

- 14 • Maarten Everaert: 0000-0002-3493-0631
- 15 • Erik Smolders: 0000-0003-3054-2444
- 16 • Mike J. McLaughlin: 0000-0001-6796-4144
- 17 • Ivan Andelkovic: 0000-0002-4570-0540
- 18 • Simon Smolders: 0000-0002-3622-2022
- 19 • Fien Degryse: 0000-0002-4875-2944

20 **Abstract**

21 Molybdenum (Mo) is an essential plant micronutrient. Despite low plant Mo requirements, deficiencies
22 are not uncommon and soluble Mo fertilizers are often applied. However, soluble Mo may result in poor
23 Mo use efficiency due to strong sorption (acid-weathered soils) or leaching (lighter-textured soils). Here,
24 ZnAl layered double hydroxides (LDHs), loaded with molybdate (MoO_4), were examined for their potential
25 as slow-release Mo compounds. Chloride-exchanged LDHs with varying Zn/Al ratio (2, 3, and 4) were
26 exchanged with MoO_4 . Zn_2Al LDH indicated MoO_4 intercalation, whereas Zn_3Al and Zn_4Al LDHs bound
27 MoO_4 merely on edge-sites. Short-term Mo-LDH incubation identified sulfate, carbonate and phosphate
28 as most competitive anions for MoO_4 exchange. Long-term Mo-LDH incubation in simulated pH-neutral
29 soil solutions demonstrated slow Mo release from Zn_2Al LDH (half-life 35 h), with a total Mo desorption
30 up to 85%. For Zn_3Al and Zn_4Al LDHs, Mo desorption was limited to <20%. Finally, several macronutrient
31 fertilizers were tested as possible carrier for Mo-LDH fertilizer compounds.

32 **Keywords**

33 Layered double hydroxide (LDH), anionic clays, slow-release fertilizer, molybdenum, micronutrient

34 **1. Introduction**

35 Molybdenum (Mo) is a microelement in soils, typically present at concentrations between 1-5 mg kg⁻¹ 1.
36 In oxic and suboxic soil conditions, Mo predominantly occurs as Mo(VI), which exists as oxyanionic
37 molybdate (MoO₄²⁻, further denoted as MoO₄). From the perspective of plant nutrition, the prevalence
38 and speciation of Mo in soils has important implications. Molybdenum is an essential micronutrient for
39 plants, and performs a vital role as a cofactor in several plant enzymes, such as nitrate reductase and
40 aldehyde oxidase². Although Mo is required by plants in very small amounts, Mo deficiencies are common
41 in high rainfall environments³⁻⁵, particularly with *Brassica* crops (*e.g.* cauliflower, rapeseed) which are
42 known for their relatively high Mo demand⁶. Two specific soil types are often linked to Mo deficiency: *i)*
43 acid weathered soils, in which MoO₄ is strongly adsorbed onto Fe/Al-oxyhydroxides⁷, and *ii)* well-drained
44 soils in high rainfall environments, where MoO₄ is prone to leaching⁸. Soil management techniques can,
45 to some extent, help to overcome Mo deficiency. For acid weathered soils with Mo deficiency, liming
46 treatments have positive effects on the Mo availability as result of a decreased MoO₄ sorption⁹, while soil
47 organic matter addition can reduce losses of Mo via leaching by improving retention in soil¹⁰.

48 In many cases, soil management (liming, organic matter application) is not sufficient to secure the Mo
49 requirements of crops, and application of Mo fertilizers is required^{11,12}. Conventional Mo fertilizers, such
50 as Na₂MoO₄ and (NH₄)₂MoO₄, are highly water-soluble Mo compounds, which can be applied to the soil
51 or be used as a foliar spray. For soil application, micronutrients such as Mo are often applied with co-
52 granulated macronutrient compounds, as this saves cost (no separate application needed) and results in
53 better distribution. Efficient Mo supply is key with regard to Mo fertilizer application, not only from the
54 perspective of providing sufficient plant-available Mo, but also from that of efficient resource usage and
55 minimization of dissipative Mo losses linked to fertilizer application¹³. Yet, soil application of soluble Mo
56 fertilizers is often associated with a low fertilizer use efficiency, due to either fast MoO₄ fixation in soil
57 after release from the fertilizer or to losses from the topsoil by leaching^{14,15}. With foliar application, these

58 issues can largely be avoided, which therefore also often results in higher Mo fertilizer effectiveness in
59 comparison with soil application¹⁶. However, foliar application is also labor intensive, and its effectiveness
60 can be very dependent on the application time¹⁷.

61 Besides the application method, application timing, rate, and fertilizer source can be important tools to
62 improve Mo fertilizer use efficiency. Slow-release Mo fertilizer compounds have the potential to reduce
63 Mo losses associated with immediate fixation or leaching. However, very limited research has been
64 performed on the development of alternative Mo fertilizer compounds with limited water solubility and
65 their potential to improve the Mo use efficiency. Bandyopadhyay *et al.* (2008) developed a slow-release
66 Mo compound based on magnesium sodium polymolybdophosphate with low water solubility, yet high
67 citrate solubility, and Hara (2015) compared three poorly-soluble Mo salts as a seed coating. Chen *et al.*
68 (2019) explored the use of Mo-slag material as an alternative micronutrient fertilizer with limited
69 solubility.

70 In this study, Mo-loaded layered double hydroxides (LDHs) are proposed for the first time as a promising
71 slow-release fertilizer compound for Mo. In brief, LDHs are layered inorganic materials, consisting of
72 positively-charged metal hydroxide layers of divalent (M^{2+}) and trivalent (M^{3+}) metal cations and an
73 interlayer gallery of electrostatically-bound anions. These intercalated anions are exchangeable when the
74 LDH is suspended in an exchange solution containing competitive counter anions. Because of this
75 particular property, LDHs were found to be suitable matrices to hold anionic nutrients, which can be
76 released slowly into the soil solution via anion exchange and/or controlled dissolution of the LDH²¹. Over
77 the past decade, many studies have explored the characteristics and the effectiveness of LDH fertilizers
78 for anionic macronutrients phosphorus (as phosphate)²²⁻²⁴ and nitrogen (as nitrate)^{25,26} and, more
79 recently, also for micronutrient boron (as borate)²⁷. In addition to the anionic nutrient species in the LDH,
80 also divalent cationic LDH components (*e.g.* Mg^{2+} or Zn^{2+}) can have nutritional value, although these are
81 only available after disintegration of the layered structure^{28,29}.

82 Against this background, the aim of this study was to gain insight in the anion-exchange properties of Mo-
83 loaded ZnAl LDHs and to assess their potential as slow-release Mo fertilizer compounds. Three Cl-
84 exchanged ZnAl LDHs with varying molar Zn/Al ratio were investigated in terms of the MoO₄ adsorption
85 capacity and the MoO₄ sorption mechanism. Subsequently, the release of MoO₄ from these LDHs was
86 examined *i)* from a mechanistic perspective, by incubating the Mo-LDHs in the presence of soil solution
87 anions, and *ii)* from a kinetic perspective, with a 3-week incubation of the Mo-LDHs in a simulated pH
88 neutral soil solution. Finally, different macronutrient compounds were examined for their suitability as
89 macronutrient carrier for a slow-release Mo-LDH fertilizer compound, by identifying changes in Mo
90 speciation and material stability of a Mo-LDH in a macronutrient environment.

91

92 **2. Materials and methods**

93 **2.1. LDH synthesis and characterization**

94 Three ZnAl LDHs were prepared by varying the molar Zn/Al ratio in the metal precursor solution between
95 either 2, 3 or 4 using a co-precipitation method at room temperature³⁰. These precursor solutions were
96 obtained by dissolving ZnCl₂ and AlCl₃·6H₂O in MilliQ™ water at the required molar ratios, while
97 maintaining a total metal concentration of 1 M. These metal solutions were added to a 200 mL MilliQ™
98 solution (adjusted to pH 9 with NaOH) at a rate of 10 mL h⁻¹ using a Perfusor pump (B. Braun). During
99 precipitation in a N₂ atmosphere, the pH was maintained at 9.0 ± 0.1 with the controlled addition of a 2 M
100 NaOH solution, performed by a Metrohm Titrino 702. After the addition of 50 mL metal solution to the
101 synthesis mixture, the material was ripened for 0.5 h at room temperature. Subsequently, the synthesis
102 mixture was treated at 70°C for 24 h in a closed vessel. Finally, the materials were recovered by
103 centrifugation, washed three times with MilliQ™ water and dried at 70°C. The LDHs obtained from the
104 metal precursor solution with a molar Zn/Al ratio of either 2, 3 or 4 were termed Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al,
105 respectively.

106 To determine the metal content of the LDHs, the dried samples were dissolved in *aqua regia* and analyzed
107 with inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES, PerkinElmer Optima 3300 DV).
108 The crystallographic characteristics of the as-synthesized LDHs were investigated with powder X-ray
109 diffraction (XRD), performed with a Malvern PANalytical Empyrean diffractometer in transmission mode,
110 using a PIXcel3D solid state detector and Cu anode (Cu K α 1: 1.5406 Å; Cu K α 2: 1.5444 Å) at a scan rate of
111 2.2° min⁻¹ and a scan range of 1.3-70°. The FTIR analysis was performed with a Bruker IFS 66v/S
112 spectrophotometer, and the SEM analysis with a PHILIPS XL 30 FG microscope on Pt coated samples.
113 Finally, nitrogen adsorption isotherms at 77 K were measured using a Micromeritics 3Flex gas
114 physisorption instrument. The samples were degassed before measurement at 393 K under vacuum (10⁻²
115 mbar) for 8 h.

116

117 **2.2. Uptake of MoO₄ by as-synthesized LDHs**

118 Adsorption isotherms were determined for the uptake of MoO₄ anions. The exchange solutions were
119 prepared by dissolving Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O, with the initial Mo concentration ranging up to 21.0 mM for Zn₂Al,
120 up to 15.8 mM for Zn₃Al and up to 12.7 mM for Zn₄Al. This way, the amount of MoO₄²⁻ in the exchange
121 solutions varied between 0% and 250% of the theoretical anion exchange capacity (AEC) of each LDH,
122 which was calculated from the weight of the LDH formula [Zn²⁺_{1-x}Al³⁺_x(OH)₂]^{x+} [Cl⁻]_x (not including the
123 weight of bound water), with x the cation isomorphic substitution ratio equal to M³⁺/(M²⁺ + M³⁺). The pH
124 of all prepared exchange solutions was adjusted to pH 7.0 using dilute HCl and NaOH solutions. The LDHs
125 were incubated in the exchange solutions at a liquid:solid ratio of 200 mL g⁻¹, and the suspensions were
126 shaken end-over-end at 20°C for 24 h (duplicate treatment). After reaction, the suspensions were
127 centrifuged (4,000 g, 20 min). The Mo concentration of the supernatants was determined with ICP-OES,
128 and also the pH of the supernatants was measured. The obtained Mo-loaded LDHs were recovered and
129 dried at 70°C, and a selection of the solid samples was analyzed with ICP-OES, XRD and FTIR.

130 **2.3. Release of MoO₄ from LDHs in the presence of soil solution anions**

131 The release of MoO₄ loaded onto Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDHs was investigated in the presence of different
132 counter anions, *i.e.* Cl, NO₃, SO₄, CO₃, and PO₄ (notation representing all species of chloride, nitrate,
133 sulfate, carbonate and phosphate, respectively). For this, Mo-LDHs were prepared according to previous
134 loading procedure at the highest Mo concentration (21.0 mM for Zn₂Al, 15.8 mM for Zn₃Al and 12.7 mM
135 for Zn₄Al), washed briefly with MilliQ™ water after centrifugation, prior to a second recovery by
136 centrifugation and drying at 70 °C. The composition of these materials was determined by ICP-OES after
137 digestion in *aqua regia*. Solutions with 20 mM of either NaCl, NaNO₃, Na₂SO₄, NaHCO₃ or NaH₂PO₄ were
138 prepared, with the pH adjusted to 8.2 (using NaOH). Additionally, a reference solution of MilliQ™ water
139 adjusted to pH 8.2 was included. The three ZnAl LDHs were incubated in these solutions at a liquid:solid
140 ratio that would allow a constant molar counter anion over AEC ratio, *i.e.* a liquid:solid ratio of 250 mL g⁻¹
141 ¹ for Mo-Zn₂Al, 185 mL g⁻¹ for Mo-Zn₃Al and 159 mL g⁻¹ for Mo-Zn₄Al. Using this approach, the selectivity
142 of the different counter anions could be compared among the different LDHs. The suspensions were
143 shaken end-over-end at 20°C for 24 h (duplicate treatment). After reaction, the suspensions were
144 centrifuged (4,000 g, 20 min). The concentrations of Mo, P and S in the supernatants were determined
145 with ICP-OES, the concentration of Cl was determined with ion chromatography (Dionex ICS2000), the
146 concentration of NO₃ with a sulfonamide colorimetric method (Skalar SA-40) and the concentration of
147 carbonate (CO₃) with total carbon analysis (Shimadzu TOC-L). Also the pH of the supernatants was
148 measured. The solid sediments after centrifugation were recovered and dried at 70°C, and a selection of
149 the solid samples was analyzed with XRD.

150

151 **2.4. Kinetics of MoO₄ release from LDHs in a simulated soil solution**

152 The kinetics of MoO₄ release from Mo-loaded Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDH was investigated in a simulated
153 soil solution. This simulated soil solution, containing 1 mM CaCl₂, 0.5 mM MgSO₄, 10 μM NaH₂PO₄, 1 mM

154 KNO₃ and 2 mM NaHCO₃³¹, was prepared by dissolving the salts and adjusting the pH of the solution to
155 7.1 using HCl (24 μL HCl L⁻¹). Using 7.5 mL of this solution, MoO₄ loaded materials of Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al
156 were transferred into dialysis membranes (Spectra/Por 4; regenerated cellulose; MWCO, 12-14 kDa;
157 diameter, 16 mm) at a rate equaling 10 mg Mo for each of the LDHs. The closed dialysis membranes with
158 Mo-LDH were, immediately after preparation, transferred into sealed plastic containers containing 922.5
159 mL simulated soil solution. Reference treatments were set up with Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O transferred in a dialysis
160 membrane or with Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O transferred directly in the containers, both also at a dose of 10 mg Mo
161 per container. All treatments were prepared in duplicate. For 504 h, the containers were shaken
162 horizontally. After 3 h, 8 h, 24 h, 48 h, 96 h, 168 h, 336 h and 504 h, 3 mL of the external solution was
163 sampled (no solution renewal) to determine the Mo concentration with ICP-OES. After 504 h incubation,
164 the pH of the external solution was measured. The dialysis membranes were recovered from the solution,
165 and digested in boiling HNO₃ using a MARS 6 microwave digestion system (CEM), followed by analysis on
166 ICP-OES to determine the residual MoO₄ in the LDHs. The kinetics of Mo release from the LDHs was
167 described with a pseudo-second-order model, often used to describe anion exchange kinetics on LDHs³²:

168
$$q_t = \frac{k q_e^2 t}{1+k q_e t} \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

169 with q_e (-) the fraction of LDH-Mo that was desorbed at equilibrium, k (h⁻¹) the rate constant, and q_t (-) the
170 fraction of LDH-Mo that was desorbed at time t (h).

171

172 **2.5. Assessment of stability and MoO₄ release of Mo-Zn₂Al in macronutrient carrier environments**

173 Co-granulation of Mo-LDH compounds with macronutrient carriers could be a possible Mo application
174 strategy. However, during a co-granulation process with conventional soluble macronutrient compounds,
175 the high ionic strength and anion concentration could compromise the stability of the LDH and the slow-
176 release Mo properties of the compound. These aspects were assessed by incubating the Mo-Zn₂Al LDH in

177 0.5 M solutions of mono-ammonium phosphate (MAP, $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$), di-ammonium phosphate (DAP,
178 $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$), muriate of potash (MOP, KCl) or urea $((\text{NH}_2)_2\text{CO})$, at a liquid:solid ratio of 200 mL g^{-1} . The
179 suspensions were shaken end-over-end at 20°C for either 1 h or 24 h. All treatments were prepared in
180 duplicate. After reaction, the suspensions were centrifuged (4,000 g, 10 min). The Mo concentration of
181 the supernatants was determined with ICP-OES, and the pH of the supernatants was measured. The solid
182 material recovered after centrifugation was briefly rinsed with MilliQ™ water to remove remaining salts,
183 after which the material was recovered again with centrifugation, dried at 70°C and analyzed with XRD.

184

185 **3. Results and discussion**

186 **3.1. Characterization of as-synthesized LDHs**

187 Three phase-pure ZnAl LDHs were obtained from the co-precipitation synthesis, as evidenced by the XRD
188 patterns of the materials (Figure 1a, Figure S1). The measured molar Zn/Al ratios of the LDHs were only
189 slightly below those of the corresponding metal precursor solutions (Table 1). From the elemental
190 composition of the as-synthesized LDHs (*i.e.*, the measured molar Zn/Al ratio), the theoretical AEC of the
191 materials was determined³⁰, which was 3.51 $\text{meq}_c \text{g}^{-1}$ for Zn_2Al , 2.70 $\text{meq}_c \text{g}^{-1}$ for Zn_3Al and 2.13 $\text{meq}_c \text{g}^{-1}$
192 for Zn_4Al (Table 1). The basal spacing decreased slightly from 7.87 Å for the Zn_4Al LDH to 7.73 Å for the
193 Zn_2Al LDH, as derived from the position of the (003) XRD reflection (Figure 1a, Table 1). Since the thickness
194 of the metal hydroxide layers is constant (4.77 Å)³³, this decrease in basal spacing could be associated to
195 a slight decrease in the interlayer spacing from 3.10 Å for the Zn_4Al LDH to 2.96 Å for the Zn_2Al LDH (Table
196 1). This trend of decreasing spacing went along with increasing layer charge and, hence, was attributed to
197 a more pronounced presence of high charge density CO_3^{2-} and OH^- anions in the LDHs with higher layer
198 charge density. A similar trend in the interlayer spacing with changing Zn/Al ratio has been observed in
199 previous studies^{34,35}. The FTIR spectra of the LDHs (Figure 1b) showed the characteristic LDH fingerprint
200 with the Zn-OH deformation band at $\sim 1500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the δ -HOH band of interlayer water at $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$,

201 in agreement with the spectra of Cl-exchanged LDH ³⁶. However, the LDH materials probably also
202 contained some traces of CO₃²⁻ anions, with the ν_2 -CO₃²⁻ band at $\sim 820\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the ν_3 -CO₃²⁻ band at ~ 1360
203 cm^{-1} ^{37,38}, despite the N₂-gas flushing during synthesis. The specific surface area of the materials increased
204 with an increasing Zn/Al ratio (Table 1), which was in line with earlier work ³⁹. The SEM micrographs of
205 the LDHs showed a characteristic LDH crystal morphology for the Zn₃Al LDH and a relatively large crystal
206 size of $\sim 2\ \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 2). For the Zn₂Al and Zn₄Al LDH, however, this morphology was less pronounced and
207 the average crystal size was smaller ($\sim 500\text{ nm}$). There was no clear relation between the specific surface
208 area and the observed crystal sizes of these materials. This could be attributed to the layered plate-like
209 morphology of LDH crystals, which does much less affect external surface area in comparison with, for
210 example, spherical crystals.

211 **Table 1** Material properties of the Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDHs.

Material	Molar Zn/Al ratio in synthesis solution	Molar Zn/Al ratio in LDHs	Theoretical AEC ^a	Zn content	Al content	Specific surface area	Basal spacing	Interlayer spacing
-	-	-	<i>meq_c g⁻¹</i>	<i>wt%</i>	<i>wt%</i>	<i>m² g⁻¹</i>	Å	Å
Zn ₂ Al	2.00	1.90	3.51	40.1	8.8	24.7	7.73	2.96
Zn ₃ Al	3.00	2.76	2.70	43.7	6.5	32.3	7.82	3.05
Zn ₄ Al	4.00	3.75	2.13	46.9	5.2	39.6	7.87	3.10

212 ^a Calculated from the weight of the LDH formula [Zn²⁺_{1-x}Al³⁺_x(OH)₂]^{x+} [Cl⁻]_x

213

214 **Figure 1** The (003) XRD reflection (a) and the FTIR spectrum (b) of the Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDHs, either in as-synthesized form
 215 (A.S.) or after reaction with MoO₄.

216

217

218 **Figure 2** SEM micrographs of the as-synthesized Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDHs.

219

220

221

222 3.2. Uptake of MoO₄ by as-synthesized LDHs

223 For the three LDHs, MoO₄ adsorption isotherms were determined to assess their capacity, selectivity and
224 adsorption mechanism for MoO₄ (Figure 3, left). In terms of the capacity for MoO₄, up to 1.38 mmol MoO₄
225 g⁻¹ could be adsorbed by Zn₂Al, while this was 1.18 mmol MoO₄ g⁻¹ for Zn₃Al and 0.83 mmol MoO₄ g⁻¹ for
226 Zn₄Al. The highest MoO₄ loading yielded a Mo content of 11.5 wt% for Zn₂Al, 9.9 wt% for Zn₃Al and 4.9 wt%
227 for Zn₄Al, after recovery and drying of the materials (Table 2). The molar Zn/Al ratio of these recovered
228 materials remained similar to that of the as-synthesized LDHs which, together with the XRD
229 characterization (Figure S2), confirmed a good stability of the materials during MoO₄ loading. Only in the
230 Zn₂Al LDH, a minor boehmite (γ-AlOOH) phase was formed during loading with MoO₄ (Figure S2). For the
231 design of a macronutrient fertilizer enriched with a micronutrient LDH phase, the Mo/Zn weight ratio in
232 the LDH can be particularly important to obtained desired Zn and Mo application doses. At highest MoO₄
233 loading, the Mo/Zn weight ratio varied between 0.32 for Zn₂Al and 0.16 for Zn₄Al (Table 2).

234
235 **Figure 3** Adsorption isotherms of MoO₄²⁻ uptake by the Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDHs, expressed as the molar Mo uptake per g
236 material (left) or as MoO₄²⁻ uptake relative to the anion exchange capacity (right). Error bars represent the standard error (n=2).
237

238 For all exchange solutions in which MoO_4 was present, the final pH was between 6.2 and 7.4 (initial pH
 239 was always 7.0) (Figure 4). Since protonation ($\text{pK}_{\text{a}1}$ of 4.00, $\text{pK}_{\text{a}2}$ of 4.24) and polymerization of MoO_4
 240 typically occur in slightly more acidic conditions, MoO_4^{2-} could be considered the dominant species in
 241 solution^{40,41}. In line with the solution speciation, the FTIR spectra of the Mo-loaded LDHs indicated that
 242 MoO_4^{2-} was also the dominant Mo species in the materials, according to *i)* the ν_3 - MoO_4^{2-} band at $\sim 820 \text{ cm}^{-1}$
 243 ¹ for Zn_2Al , or at $\sim 785 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for Zn_3Al and Zn_4Al and *ii)* the absence of the characteristic bands of polymeric
 244 MoO_4 (e.g. $\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}^{6-}$, at $\sim 895 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 930 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (Figure 1b)⁴¹⁻⁴³. The absolute MoO_4 uptake by the LDHs
 245 increased with a decreasing Zn/Al ratio of the material. Yet, at maximum loading, the uptake of MoO_4 (as
 246 MoO_4^{2-}) by the LDHs relative to their theoretical AEC remained fairly similar for the three LDHs (Figure 3,
 247 right), an observation that was also supported by the comparable molar Mo/Al ratios (~ 0.4) of the
 248 obtained materials (Table 2).

249 **Figure 4** The final solution pH of the MoO_4 exchange solutions with or without incubation of ZnAl LDH, presented relative to the
 250 initial amount of MoO_4^{2-} added to the exchange solution. The open dots present the pH of the blank exchange solutions (no LDH).
 251 Error bars represent the standard error ($n=2$).
 252

253

254 The XRD pattern of the Zn_2Al LDH showed a strong increase of the interlayer spacing from 2.96 \AA to 3.83 \AA
 255 as result of loading with MoO_4 (Figure 1a, Table 2), which was attributed to the intercalation of MoO_4^{2-}
 256 anions^{44,45}. Sorption of MoO_4 on Zn_2Al LDH thus likely occurred on interlayer sites, and also partly on edge
 257 sites. However, for the Zn_3Al and Zn_4Al LDHs, no such increase of the interlayer spacing, and even a slight

258 decrease, was recorded as result of incubation in the MoO_4 solution. This difference in intercalation
259 behavior between the Zn_2Al LDH and two other LDHs was linked to differences in affinity of interlayer
260 sorption sites for divalent MoO_4^{2-} between these materials. The maximum MoO_4 adsorption capacity
261 increased with an increasing material charge density ($\text{Zn}_2\text{Al} > \text{Zn}_3\text{Al} > \text{Zn}_4\text{Al}$). The high MoO_4 selectivity of
262 the interlayer sites of Zn_2Al LDH could be attributed to the fact that divalent MoO_4^{2-} anions were more
263 effective at compensating the high layer charge in the interlayer gallery of this LDH in comparison with
264 the monovalent Cl^- anions initially present on the exchange complex. Therefore, the Zn_2Al LDH, on the one
265 hand, favored the intercalation of MoO_4^{2-} anions as a result of its high layer charge density, which resulted
266 in the desorption of Cl^- and an increase of the interlayer spacing. With the Zn_3Al and Zn_4Al LDH, on the
267 other hand, the interlayer Cl^- was probably partly exchanged with slightly smaller $\text{OH}^-/\text{HCO}_3^-$ anions, while
268 MoO_4^{2-} anions were merely adsorbed on the edge sites of these LDHs. This competitiveness of OH^- anions
269 for intercalation in LDHs was also illustrated by the decrease in solution pH in the absence of MoO_4 (Figure
270 4). At an increasing initial MoO_4 concentration in the exchange solution, the pH decrease was less
271 pronounced as a result of MoO_4^{2-} acting as a weak base⁴⁴. The pronounced presence of CO_3 was evidenced
272 by the IR bands at $\sim 680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 818 cm^{-1} (Figure 1b).

273

274 Given the difference in intercalation behavior between the Zn_2Al LDH and the Zn_3Al or Zn_4Al LDH, the
275 comparable MoO_4 uptake relative to the respective AEC of the different LDHs was surprising. Likely, this
276 could be attributed to the fact that the Zn_3Al and Zn_4Al LDH compensated for the absence of MoO_4
277 sorption on interlayer sites with a more pronounced sorption on edge sites in comparison with the Zn_2Al
278 LDH, which could be linked to the higher specific surface area of the as-synthesized Zn_3Al and Zn_4Al LDH
279 (Table 1). Furthermore, it could be hypothesized that, with the LDHs with a high molar Zn/Al ratio (*i.e.*
280 Zn_3Al , Zn_4Al), the Al cations were unevenly distributed in the basal plane and situated merely at the edge
281 of the plane (Figure S3), which allowed a significant MoO_4 sorption on the outer surface. However, in LDH

282 synthesis conditions with a lower molar Zn/Al ratio (*e.g.* synthesis of Zn₂Al), a more evenly Al distribution
 283 across the basal plane was warranted by the repulsion between Al cations in neighboring octahedral units.
 284 Therefore, in order for MoO₄ to access the interlayer Al sorption sites of Zn₂Al, MoO₄ intercalation was
 285 required.

286 **Table 2** Material properties of the MoO₄²⁻ loaded Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDHs.

Material	Molar Zn/Al	Mo content <i>wt%</i>	Zn content <i>wt%</i>	Al content <i>wt%</i>	Weight Mo/Zn ratio	Molar Mo/Al ratio	Basal spacing Å	Interlayer spacing Å
Mo-Zn ₂ Al	1.93	11.5	36.4	7.8	0.32	0.42	8.60	3.83
Mo-Zn ₃ Al	2.86	9.9	39.6	5.7	0.25	0.49	7.59	2.82
Mo-Zn ₄ Al	3.83	4.9	45.4	4.9	0.16	0.42	7.69	2.92

287

288

289 3.3. Release of MoO₄ from LDHs in the presence of single soil solution anions

290 The exchangeability of MoO₄ in the three Mo-loaded LDHs was assessed in solutions containing varying
 291 soil solutions anions (Figure S4, Figure 5). For all LDHs, the exchange solutions containing SO₄, CO₃ or PO₄
 292 anions were most effective at exchanging MoO₄ from the materials (for Mo-Zn₂Al: 45% with SO₄, 28% with
 293 CO₃ and 48% with PO₄), which was in line with findings for anion selectivity with ZnAl LDHs in previous
 294 studies^{46,47}. However, the relative MoO₄ exchangeability from the three LDH differed substantially (Figure
 295 S4). With Mo-Zn₂Al, much more MoO₄ could be desorbed (up to 48% with PO₄) in comparison with Mo-
 296 Zn₃Al (up to 12% with SO₄) and Mo-Zn₄Al (also up to 12% with SO₄). This was attributed to the nature of
 297 the interaction of MoO₄ in the three LDH materials. In the Mo-Zn₂Al LDH, a large fraction of MoO₄ was
 298 likely bound electrostatically in the interlayer (Figure 1a), which can be considered a well-exchangeable
 299 MoO₄ fraction in the presence of competitive anions. The release of intercalated MoO₄ from Zn₂Al during
 300 this incubation, as evidenced by XRD, was particularly clear in the presence of strongly competitive
 301 counter anions SO₄, CO₃ and PO₄ (Figure 6)⁴⁸. With the Mo-Zn₃Al and Mo-Zn₄Al LDHs, however,
 302 intercalated MoO₄ was not detected. Hence, MoO₄ sorption with Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al likely occurred on edge

303 sites, likely via a combination of inner-sphere MoO_4 complexes on the LDH crystal edges, resulting in a
 304 poorly-exchangeable pool of MoO_4 , and, to a lesser extent, electrostatically bound MoO_4 . During the
 305 incubation of $\text{Mo-Zn}_3\text{Al}$ and $\text{Mo-Zn}_4\text{Al}$, anion exchange reactions took place on the outer surface, and not
 306 in the interlayer gallery, as shown by XRD (Figure 6). The clear difference between intercalated and
 307 surface-bound MoO_4 in terms of exchangeability from LDHs was also in line with earlier observations for
 308 PO_4 anions in LDHs⁴⁹. Finally, it was noted that for $\text{Mo-Zn}_2\text{Al}$ and $\text{Mo-Zn}_3\text{Al}$, mainly MoO_4 was desorbed,
 309 whereas for $\text{Mo-Zn}_4\text{Al}$ also a significant amount of Cl^- anions was desorbed.

310
 311 **Figure 5** The anion exchange of Mo-loaded Zn_2Al , Zn_3Al and Zn_4Al LDHs incubated in solutions containing varying soil solution
 312 anions, presented on a scale molar charge exchange, with the anions desorbed in this reaction on the positive axis and the
 313 adsorbed anions on the negative axis. The values above the bars represent the relative MoO_4 desorption from the materials in
 314 the different conditions, while the values below the bars represent the final pH of the respective exchange solution.

315
 316 The anion exchange could also be interpreted from a molar charge perspective, based on a hypothesized
 317 speciation of the included anions (Figure 5). For several anions, such as Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} and MoO_4^{2-} , the
 318 anion speciation was straightforward for the investigated conditions. Charge calculations were also
 319 performed with an assumed CO_3 speciation of HCO_3^- and PO_4 speciation of HPO_4^{2-} , both dominant anion
 320 species at the initial solution pH of 8.2. Equilibrated charge balances were obtained for the three LDHs
 321 incubated in the presence of competitive counter anions SO_4^{2-} , HCO_3^- and, to some extent, HPO_4^{2-} . While
 322 the assumed speciation of divalent SO_4^{2-} and monovalent HCO_3^- fitted the charge balance with MoO_4^{2-} and
 323 Cl^- desorption, the assumption of HPO_4^{2-} adsorption by anion exchange with MoO_4^{2-} and Cl^- resulted in an

324 overestimation of the adsorbed anion charge. For the Zn₂Al LDH, this was explained by the fact that likely
325 PO₄ was intercalated as HPO₄²⁻, thereby exchanging MoO₄²⁻, but that additional PO₄ was removed from
326 the solution due to the formation of a Zn-PO₄ precipitate (Figure S5)⁵⁰. For the Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDHs, it
327 was expected that PO₄ was likely adsorbed on the edge sites in a mixed HPO₄²⁻/H₂PO₄⁻ speciation. Overall,
328 in the presence of strongly competitive counter anions (SO₄, CO₃, PO₄), the release of MoO₄ via anion
329 exchange was clearly dominated by the presence of these counter anions and their respective anion
330 speciation. However, in the exchange solutions containing the less competitive Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻ anions, or in
331 absence of added counter anions, the measured counter anions could not account for the determined
332 MoO₄²⁻/Cl⁻ release, with a single exception of NO₃⁻ sorption on Mo-Zn₃Al. The poor prediction of the MoO₄
333 release via the adsorption of these less competitive anions was attributed to the contribution of OH⁻ in
334 the anion exchange. In the absence of other competitive counter anions, OH⁻ strongly contributed to the
335 exchange of MoO₄²⁻ and Cl⁻. This was also evidenced by the relatively low pH obtained for the Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ and
336 reference water solutions (Figure 5).

337

338 **Figure 6** The (003) XRD reflection of the Mo-loaded Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDHs before incubation, and after incubation *i*) in the
 339 presence of soil solution anions Cl, NO₃, SO₄, CO₃ and PO₄ or *ii*) in absence of counter anions. The basal spacing is reported next
 340 to the (003) XRD reflection.

341 3.4. Kinetics of MoO₄ release from LDHs and soluble Na₂MoO₄ in a simulated soil solution

342 The incubation study in the presence of single counter anions showed that anions SO₄, CO₃ and PO₄ were
 343 most effective at replacing MoO₄ on the exchange complex of the LDHs. However, if Mo-loaded LDHs are
 344 incubated in a soil system, MoO₄ release will not only be driven by the selectivity of the LDHs towards the
 345 different soil solution anions, but also by the relative abundance of these counter anions in the soil
 346 solution. Therefore, the release kinetics of MoO₄ from the LDHs were determined in a simulated soil
 347 solution with relevant concentrations of inorganic soil solution anions (Figure 7), and described by a
 348 pseudo-second-order kinetic model (Table 3). The low MoO₄ exchangeability in the Mo-Zn₃Al and Mo-
 349 Zn₄Al LDHs, as described in the previous release experiment (Figure 5), was also shown in this kinetic
 350 desorption trial, with only 15% of MoO₄ released from Mo-Zn₃Al and 19% from Mo-Zn₄Al LDHs after 504

351 h (3 weeks). However, a much higher MoO₄ exchangeability was obtained with the Mo-Zn₂Al material,
352 which released up to 85% of MoO₄ over a course of 3 weeks. Digestion of the residues at the end of the
353 experiment indicated that 16% of MoO₄ from the Mo-Zn₂Al was not desorbed, while retained Mo was 86%
354 for Zn₃Al and 77% for Zn₄Al LDH. These values largely confirmed the Mo mass balance between the
355 amount of desorbed Mo and the amount of Mo remaining in the LDH materials (total recoveries between
356 96% and 101%).

357 Half of the desorbable MoO₄ fraction of the Mo-Zn₂Al LDH was released after 33.8 h, while for the Mo-
358 Zn₃Al LDH this was already after 7.1 h and for the Mo-Zn₄Al LDH after 11.4 h. This indicated that not only
359 less MoO₄ could be released from the Mo-Zn₃Al and Mo-Zn₄Al LDHs in a pH neutral solution, but also that
360 the MoO₄ release from these LDHs could be considered less slow in comparison with the LDH with
361 intercalated MoO₄. The pronounced slow release of intercalated MoO₄ from Mo-Zn₂Al LDH was linked to
362 the counter diffusion limitations in the interlayer gallery, caused by MoO₄ diffusion towards to crystal
363 edges and diffusion of soil solution anions from the crystal edges⁴⁹. In actual soil conditions, it is expected
364 that the MoO₄ release from the Mo-Zn₃Al and Mo-Zn₄Al LDHs could continue over time because *i)* rather
365 than in this batch experiment, MoO₄ is also removed from the soil solution (*e.g.* via plant uptake), which
366 will be an additional driving force for MoO₄ desorption, and *ii)* a slow dissolution of the LDH matrix in
367 slightly acidic soil conditions can contribute to MoO₄ release. Finally, it could be noted that, during the
368 incubation, the pH of the external solutions increased slightly from 7.1 to ~8.1 (Table S1), but did not vary
369 largely between the treatments.

370

371

372

373 **Table 3** Pseudo-second-order kinetic parameters of the MoO₄ desorption from the Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDH in a simulated soil
 374 solution.

	q _e	k	r ²
	-	h ⁻¹	-
Zn ₂ Al	0.904	0.033	0.99
Zn ₃ Al	0.155	0.910	0.99
Zn ₄ Al	0.196	0.447	0.99

375

376

377 **Figure 7** The MoO₄ release kinetics from Mo-Zn₂Al, Mo-Zn₃Al, Mo-Zn₄Al and Na₂MoO₄ loaded in dialysis membranes and
 378 incubated in a simulated soil solution, plotted with pseudo-second order model. As a reference treatment, also Na₂MoO₄
 379 incubated in a simulated soil solution (without dialysis membrane) was included. Error bars represent the standard error (n=2).

380

381 3.5. Assessment of stability and MoO₄ release of Mo-Zn₂Al in macronutrient carrier environments

382 Several possible strategies exist for the application of a slow-release Mo-LDH fertilizer, such as application
 383 as a suspension, as a seed coating or as a co-granulation product with conventional soluble macronutrient
 384 compounds (termed macronutrient carrier)⁴. Clearly, for each of these approaches there are additional
 385 factors that could influence the MoO₄ release kinetics on top of the release as determined in simulated
 386 soil conditions. Especially with the latter strategy of macronutrient carriers there are concerns regarding
 387 the effect of a co-granulation process on the MoO₄ speciation in Mo-loaded LDHs. Incubation of Mo-Zn₂Al

388 LDH in concentrated solutions of MAP, DAP, MOP and urea, showed that maintaining the Mo-Zn₂Al LDH
389 phase was particularly challenging in a DAP solution, as 22% of MoO₄ was released after 1 h and 55% after
390 24 h incubation (Figure 8). This high MoO₄ release in the DAP solution was associated with *i*) the loss of
391 structural integrity, linked with the release of Zn and Al and the formation of a several Zn-PO₄ precipitates
392 (Figure 9) ⁵⁰⁻⁵², and *ii*) the release of intercalated MoO₄ due to competition with solution PO₄, likely in the
393 form of HPO₄²⁻. In contrast, the release of MoO₄ remained fairly limited in the MAP solution, with only
394 13% of MoO₄ released after 24 h. The stability of Mo-Zn₂Al was compromised to some extent, as illustrated
395 by the XRD pattern, the increase in solution pH and the dissolution of Zn. The relatively low MoO₄ release
396 in the MAP solution in comparison with in the DAP solution could at least partly be attributed to the fact
397 that intercalated MoO₄ could not be exchanged with solution PO₄ of the MAP solution (Figure 9), because
398 the main PO₄ species in the MAP solution was H₂PO₄⁻, which likely has lower exchange selectivity with
399 MoO₄²⁻ than HPO₄²⁻. In a MOP solution, 16 % of MoO₄ was released after 1 h and 27% after 24 h. The high
400 chloride concentration of the MOP solution did not compromise the LDH stability, but the asymmetric
401 (003) reflection indicated that a significant amount of intercalated MoO₄²⁻ anions were exchanged with
402 Cl⁻ anions. The most limited effect of macronutrient carrier solutions on MoO₄ release and LDH stability
403 was recorded for urea, with a Zn, Mo and Al release close to that in MilliQ™ water. This could be explained
404 by the fact that urea, unlike MAP, DAP and MOP, does not contain anionic species, and thus did not initiate
405 the release of MoO₄ via anion exchange in a concentrated solution. Hence, based on these results, the
406 incorporation of the slow-releasing Mo-loaded ZnAl LDH compound in urea fertilizer granules appears to
407 be a promising application strategy. However, next to the direct effects of soluble macronutrient
408 compounds on the release of Mo from Mo-LDH, also indirect effects can be expected to play a role when
409 a Mo-LDH macronutrient co-granulation product is applied to a soil. For example, in soils urease enzymes
410 quickly convert urea to ammonia and carbonate, thereby creating a local environment that could affect
411 the Mo-Zn₂Al LDH compound much more than shown in a chemical incubation test ⁵³. Also the local

412 competition for soil sorption sites between nutrients derived from the same co-granulation product (*e.g.*
 413 PO₄ and MoO₄) could strongly influence the plant availability of the applied Mo^{54,55}. Finally, regarding the
 414 choice of a macronutrient carrier for the Mo-LDH fertilizer, also the crop requirements should be
 415 considered. Therefore, for legume crops, the Mo-LDH fertilizer would ideally not be incorporated in a N
 416 carrier (*e.g.* urea), but rather in a P or K carrier product.

417
 418 **Figure 8** The relative Zn, Mo and Al release associated to the incubation of Mo-Zn₂Al LDH material (1 h or 24 h) in MilliQ™ water
 419 and in concentrated solutions of monoammonium phosphate (MAP), diammonium phosphate (DAP), muriate of potash (MOP)
 420 and urea. Below the graph, the final pH values of the suspensions are given, whereas the initial pH values of the tested solutions
 421 were ~7.00 for MilliQ™, 4.09 for MAP, 8.04 for DAP, 5.82 for MOP and 6.82 for urea. Error bars represent the standard error
 422 (n=2).

423

424 **Figure 9** The XRD patterns of the Mo-loaded Zn₂Al LDH before incubation, and after 24 h incubation in concentrated solutions of
 425 monoammonium phosphate (MAP), diammonium phosphate (DAP), muriate of potash (MOP) and urea or in MilliQ™ water. The
 426 basal spacing is reported next to the (003) XRD reflection.

427

428 With regard to the application of Mo-loaded ZnAl LDH to agricultural soils, two additional chemical aspects
 429 of these materials remain of interest for further research. Firstly, this study described the MoO₄ release
 430 from ZnAl LDHs in a pH neutral simulated soil solution, in which the stability of the LDH materials was
 431 guaranteed and the MoO₄ release associated to anion exchange could be characterized. However, in more
 432 acid soil conditions, the stability of ZnAl LDH can be compromised. As such, also MoO₄ release via
 433 controlled LDH dissolution would be an important Mo release mechanism. A second aspect, also linked to
 434 the dissolution of Mo-ZnAl LDHs, is the contribution of LDH-Zn as a source of Zn for plants. In acid
 435 conditions, controlled LDH dissolution can result in a slow release of Zn. Although this mechanism has

436 been investigated ²⁹, more work could be performed on the development of LDH matrices for the release
437 of a range of anionic and cationic micronutrients, *e.g.* Zn and Mo.

438

439 To conclude, this study investigated the properties of Mo-loaded ZnAl LDHs for the use of Mo-LDHs as a
440 slow-release fertilizer compound for Mo. Intercalation of MoO₄ anions in the LDH material proved to be
441 a determining factor to obtain slow but rather complete MoO₄ exchangeability:

- 442 - The loading of the Zn₂Al LDH with MoO₄ resulted in a clear intercalation of MoO₄ anions. Intercalated
443 MoO₄ was exchangeable in the presence of competitive counter anions (SO₄, CO₃ and PO₄), and up to
444 85% of the MoO₄ from this LDH could be released in a slow manner. This slow-release behavior was
445 likely linked to solid-state diffusion processes in the interlayers;
- 446 - In the case of the Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDHs, no detectable MoO₄ intercalation occurred during loading
447 with MoO₄. Only 20% of adsorbed MoO₄ in these materials proved to be available for release via anion
448 exchange and that reaction was faster than in the case of the interlayer MoO₄.

449 Different macronutrient fertilizer compounds (MAP, DAP, MOP, urea) were evaluated as carriers for the
450 performant Mo-Zn₂Al LDH compound. Urea was identified as a promising macronutrient carrier for a Mo-
451 loaded ZnAl LDH fertilizer, since the MoO₄ speciation in the LDH and the structural LDH properties were
452 well preserved in a concentrated urea solution. However, for Mo application to legume crops, also the
453 incorporation of Mo-LDH in P or K carrier products should be considered. Future work will focus on
454 chemical stability in acid conditions, soil incubation trials and fertilizer trials to unravel the benefits of this
455 new slow-release Mo compound compared to soluble Mo with respect to overcoming losses of applied
456 Mo via fixation or leaching.

457

458

459 **Associated content**

460 The Supporting Information contains additional characterization of the materials (XRD), details of the
461 exchange experiments and a graphical representation on the hypothesized distribution of metal cations
462 in the basal LDH plane.

463

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471 **References**

- 472 (1) Oorts, K.; Smolders, E.; McGrath, S. P.; Van Gestel, C. A. M.; McLaughlin, M. J.; Carey, S. Derivation of Ecological Standards
473 for Risk Assessment of Molybdate in Soil. *Environ. Chem.* **2016**, *13* (1), 168–180. <https://doi.org/10.1071/EN15086>.
- 474 (2) Kaiser, B. N.; Gridley, K. L.; Brady, J. N.; Phillips, T.; Tyerman, S. D. The Role of Molybdenum in Agricultural Plant
475 Production. *Ann. Bot.* **2005**, *96* (5), 745–754. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mci226>.
- 476 (3) Mao, X.; Li, Q.; Ren, L.; Bai, W.; Zhang, W. H. Application of Molybdenum Fertilizer Enhanced Quality and Production of
477 Alfalfa in Northern China under Non-Irrigated Conditions. *J. Plant Nutr.* **2018**, *41* (8), 1009–1019.
478 <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904167.2018.1431672>.
- 479 (4) Reisenauer, H. M. Relative Efficiency of Seed-and-Soil-Applied Molybdenum Fertilizer. *Agron. J.* **1963**, *55* (5), 459–460.
480 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2134/agronj1963.00021962005500050015x>.
- 481 (5) Barbosa, E. P. A.; Sodre, D. N.; Braun, H.; Vieira, R. F. Seeds Enriched with Molybdenum Improve Cowpea Yield in Sub-
482 Humid Tropical Regions of Brazil. *Agron. J.* **2021**, *113* (2), 2044–2052. <https://doi.org/10.1002/agj2.20596>.
- 483 (6) Hewitt, E. J.; Bolle-Jones, E. W. Molybdenum as a Plant Nutrient: II. The Effects of Molybdenum Deficiency on Some
484 Horticultural and Agricultural Crop Plants in Sand Culture. *J. Hortic. Sci.* **1952**, *27* (4), 257–265.
485 <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221589.1952.11513763>.
- 486 (7) Brennan, R. F.; Bolland, M. D. A. Increased Concentration of Molybdenum in Sown Wheat Seed Decreases Grain Yield
487 Responses to Applied Molybdenum Fertilizer in Naturally Acidic Sandplain Soils. *J. Plant Nutr.* **2007**, *30* (12), 2005–2019.
488 <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904160701700442>.
- 489 (8) Grigg, J. L. The Distribution of Molybdenum in the Soils of New Zealand. *New Zeal. J. Agric. Res.* **1960**, *3* (1), 69–86.
490 <https://doi.org/10.1080/00288233.1960.10419862>.
- 491 (9) Mandal, B.; Pal, S.; Mandal, L. N. Effect of Molybdenum, Phosphorus, and Lime Application to Acid Soils on Dry Matter
492 Yield and Molybdenum Nutrition of Lentil. *J. Plant Nutr.* **1998**, *21* (1), 139–147.
493 <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904169809365388>.
- 494 (10) Wichard, T.; Mishra, B.; Myneni, S. C. B.; Bellenger, J. P.; Kraepiel, A. M. L. Storage and Bioavailability of Molybdenum in
495 Soils Increased by Organic Matter Complexation. *Nat. Geosci.* **2009**, *2* (9), 625–630. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo589>.

- 496 (11) Content, M.; Soils, A. Effect and Interaction of Molybdenum and Limestone on Growth and Molybdenum Content of
497 Cauliflower, Alfalfa, and Bromegrass on Acid Soils. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* **1969**, No. 204, 929–932.
- 498 (12) Giddens, J.; Perkins, H. F. Essentiality of Molybdenum for Alfalfa on Highly Oxidized Piedmont Soils. *Agron. J.* **1972**, *64*
499 (6), 819–820. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2134/agronj1972.00021962006400060035x>.
- 500 (13) Henckens, M. L. C. M.; Driessen, P. P. J.; Worrell, E. Molybdenum Resources: Their Depletion and Safeguarding for Future
501 Generations. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **2018**, *134* (March), 61–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.03.002>.
- 502 (14) Riley, M. M.; Robson, A. D.; Gartrell, J. W.; Jeffery, R. C. The Absence of Leaching of Molybdenum in Acidic Soils from
503 Western Australia. *Aust. J. Soil Res.* **1987**, *25* (2), 179–184. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR9870179>.
- 504 (15) Johansen, C.; Kerridge, P. C.; Luck, P. E.; Cook, B. G.; Lowe, K. F.; Ostrowski, H. The Residual Effect of Molybdenum
505 Fertilizer on Growth of Tropical Pasture Legumes in a Sub-Tropical Environment. *Aust. J. Exp. Agric.* **1977**, *17* (89), 961–
506 968.
- 507 (16) Weir, R. G.; Nagle, R. K.; Noonan, J. B.; Towner, A. G. W. The Effect of Foliar and Soil Applied Molybdenum Treatments
508 on the Molybdenum Concentration of Maize Grain. *Aust. J. Exp. Agric.* **1976**, *16* (82), 761–764.
- 509 (17) Vieira, R. F.; Cardoso, E. J. B. N.; Vieira, C.; Cassini, S. T. A. Foliar Application of Molybdenum in Common Beans. I.
510 Nitrogenase and Reductase Activities in a Soil of High Fertility. *J. Plant Nutr.* **1998**, *21* (1), 169–180.
511 <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904169809365391>.
- 512 (18) Bandyopadhyay, S.; Bhattacharya, I.; Ghosh, K.; Varadachari, C. New Slow-Releasing Molybdenum Fertilizer. *J. Agric.*
513 *Food Chem.* **2008**, *56* (4), 1343–1349. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf072878g>.
- 514 (19) Hara, Y. Improvement of Soybean Seedling Establishment under a Flooded Condition by Seed Coating with Molybdenum
515 Compounds. *Plant Prod. Sci.* **2015**, *18* (2), 161–165. <https://doi.org/10.1626/pps.18.161>.
- 516 (20) Chen, D.; Meng, Z. wen; Chen, Y. ping. Toxicity Assessment of Molybdenum Slag as a Mineral Fertilizer: A Case Study
517 with Pakchoi (*Brassica Chinensis* L.). *Chemosphere* **2019**, *217* (97), 816–824.
518 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.10.216>.
- 519 (21) Gillman, G.; Noble, A. Environmentally Manageable Fertilizers: A New Approach. *Environ. Qual. Manag.* **2005**, *15* (2), 59–
520 70. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tqem.20081>.

- 521 (22) Everaert, M.; Warrinnier, R.; Baken, S.; Gustafsson, J.-P.; De Vos, D.; Smolders, E. Phosphate-Exchanged Mg-Al Layered
522 Double Hydroxides: A New Slow Release Phosphate Fertilizer. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2016**, *4* (8).
523 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.6b00778>.
- 524 (23) Everaert, M.; Degryse, F.; McLaughlin, M. J.; De Vos, D.; Smolders, E. Agronomic Effectiveness of Granulated and
525 Powdered P-Exchanged Mg-Al LDH Relative to Struvite and MAP. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **2017**, *65* (32), 6736–6744.
526 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.7b01031>.
- 527 (24) Benício, L. P. F.; Constantino, V. R. L.; Pinto, F. G.; Vergütz, L.; Tronto, J.; Da Costa, L. M. Layered Double Hydroxides: New
528 Technology in Phosphate Fertilizers Based on Nanostructured Materials. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2017**, *5* (1), 399–409.
529 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.6b01784>.
- 530 (25) da Silva, V.; Kamogawa, M. Y.; Marangoni, R.; Mangrich, A. S.; Wypych, F. Layered Double Hydroxides as Matrices for
531 Nitrate Slow Release Fertilizers. *Rev. Bras. Ciência do Solo* **2014**, *38* (1), 272–277. [https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-](https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-06832014000100027)
532 [06832014000100027](https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-06832014000100027).
- 533 (26) Berber, M. R.; Hafez, I. H.; Minagawa, K.; Mori, T. A Sustained Controlled Release Formulation of Soil Nitrogen Based on
534 Nitrate-Layered Double Hydroxide Nanoparticle Material. *J. Soils Sediments* **2014**, *14* (1), 60–66.
535 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-013-0766-3>.
- 536 (27) de Castro, G. F.; Ferreira, J. A.; Zotarelli, L.; Mattiello, E. M.; Novais, R. F.; Tronto, J. Layered Double Hydroxides
537 Intercalated with Borate: Effect of Fertilization on Boron Leaching and Successive Sunflower Cultivations. *New J. Chem.*
538 **2020**. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9nj04952e>.
- 539 (28) Songkhum, P.; Wuttikhun, T.; Chanlek, N.; Khemthong, P.; Laohasurayotin, K. Controlled Release Studies of Boron and
540 Zinc from Layered Double Hydroxides as the Micronutrient Hosts for Agricultural Application. *Appl. Clay Sci.* **2018**, *152*
541 (September), 311–322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2017.11.028>.
- 542 (29) López-Rayó, S.; Imran, A.; Bruun Hansen, H. C.; Schjoerring, J. K.; Magid, J. Layered Double Hydroxides: Potential Release-
543 on-Demand Fertilizers for Plant Zinc Nutrition. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **2017**, *65* (40), 8779–8789.
544 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.7b02604>.
- 545 (30) Everaert, M.; Dox, K.; Steele, J. A.; De Vos, D.; Smolders, E. Solid-State Speciation of Interlayer Anions in Layered Double
546 Hydroxides. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2019**, *537*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2018.11.010>.

- 547 (31) Menzie, N.; Guppy, C. In-Situ Soil Solution Extraction with Polyacrylonitrile Hollow-Fibers. *Commun. Soil Sci. Plant Anal.*
548 **2000**, *31* (11–14), 1875–1886. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00103620009370544>.
- 549 (32) Luo, L.; Guo, Q.; Cao, Y. Uptake of Aqueous Tungsten and Molybdenum by a Nitrate Intercalated, Pyroaurite-like Anion
550 Exchangeable Clay. *Appl. Clay Sci.* **2019**, *180* (June), 105179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2019.105179>.
- 551 (33) Miyata, S. The Syntheses of Hydrotalcite-Like Compounds and Their Structures and Physico-Chemical Properties—I: The
552 Systems $Mg^{2+}-Al^{3+}-NO_3^-$, $Mg^{2+}-Al^{3+}-Cl^-$, $Mg^{2+}-Al^{3+}-ClO_4^-$, $Ni^{2+}-Al^{3+}-Cl^-$ and $Zn^{2+}-Al^{3+}-Cl^-$. *Clays Clay Miner.* **1975**,
553 *23* (5), 369–375. <https://doi.org/10.1346/CCMN.1975.0230508>.
- 554 (34) Chitrakar, R.; Tezuka, S.; Sonoda, A.; Sakane, K.; Hirotsu, T. A New Method for Synthesis of Mg-Al, Mg-Fe, and Zn-Al
555 Layered Double Hydroxides and Their Uptake Properties of Bromide Ion. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2008**, *47* (14), 4905–4908.
556 <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie0716417>.
- 557 (35) Hatami, H.; Fotovat, A.; Halajnia, A. Comparison of Adsorption and Desorption of Phosphate on Synthesized Zn-Al LDH
558 by Two Methods in a Simulated Soil Solution. *Appl. Clay Sci.* **2018**, *152* (December 2017), 333–341.
559 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2017.11.032>.
- 560 (36) He, H.; Kang, H.; Ma, S.; Bai, Y.; Yang, X. High Adsorption Selectivity of ZnAl Layered Double Hydroxides and the Calcined
561 Materials toward Phosphate. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2010**, *343* (1), 225–231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2009.11.004>.
- 562 (37) Tanaka, T.; Kameshima, Y.; Nishimoto, S.; Miyake, M. Determination of Carbonate Ion Contents in Layered Double
563 Hydroxides by FTIR Spectrometry. *Anal. Methods* **2012**, *4* (12), 3925–3927. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c2ay25850a>.
- 564 (38) Klopogge, J. T.; Wharton, D.; Hickey, L.; Frost, R. L. Infrared and Raman Study of Interlayer Anions CO_3^{2-} , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-}
565 and ClO_4^- in Mg/Al- Hydrotalcite. *Am. Mineral.* **2002**, *87* (Titulaer 1993), 623–629.
- 566 (39) Olf, H. W.; Torres-Dorante, L. O.; Eckelt, R.; Kosslick, H. Comparison of Different Synthesis Routes for Mg-Al Layered
567 Double Hydroxides (LDH): Characterization of the Structural Phases and Anion Exchange Properties. *Appl. Clay Sci.* **2009**,
568 *43* (3–4), 459–464. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2008.10.009>.
- 569 (40) Goldberg, S. Competitive Adsorption of Molybdenum in the Presence of Phosphorus or Sulfur on Gibbsite. *Soil Sci.* **2010**,
570 *175* (3), 105–110. <https://doi.org/10.1097/SS.0b013e3181d3462f>.
- 571 (41) Nejati, K.; Akbari, A. R.; Davari, S.; Asadpour-Zeynali, K.; Rezvani, Z. Zn-Fe-Layered Double Hydroxide Intercalated with
572 Vanadate and Molybdate Anions for Electrocatalytic Water Oxidation. *New J. Chem.* **2018**, *42* (4), 2889–2895.

- 573 <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7nj04469k>.
- 574 (42) Jin, L.; Zeng, H. Y.; Du, J. Z.; Xu, S. Intercalation of Organic and Inorganic Anions into Layered Double Hydroxides for
575 Polymer Flame Retardancy. *Appl. Clay Sci.* **2020**, *187* (January), 105481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2020.105481>.
- 576 (43) Yan, H.; Wang, J.; Zhang, Y.; Hu, W. Preparation and Inhibition Properties of Molybdate Intercalated ZnAlCe Layered
577 Double Hydroxide. *J. Alloys Compd.* **2016**, *678*, 171–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.03.281>.
- 578 (44) Davantès, A.; Lefèvre, G. In Situ Real Time Infrared Spectroscopy of Sorption of (Poly)Molybdate Ions into Layered Double
579 Hydroxides. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2013**, *117* (48), 12922–12929. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp408885k>.
- 580 (45) Huo, W.; Cao, T.; Liu, X.; Xu, W.; Dong, B.; Zhang, Y.; Dong, F. Anion Intercalated Layered-Double-Hydroxide Structure for
581 Efficient Photocatalytic NO Remove. *Green Energy Environ.* **2019**, *4* (3), 270–277.
582 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gee.2018.11.001>.
- 583 (46) Arda, C.; Frau, F.; Dore, E.; Lattanzi, P. Molybdate Sorption by Zn-Al Sulphate Layered Double Hydroxides. *Appl. Clay
584 Sci.* **2012**, *65–66*, 128–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2012.05.005>.
- 585 (47) Koilraj, P.; Srinivasan, K. ZnAl Layered Double Hydroxides as Potential Molybdate Sorbents and Valorize the Exchanged
586 Sorbent for Catalytic Wet Peroxide Oxidation of Phenol. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2013**, *52* (22), 7373–7381.
587 <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie302782c>.
- 588 (48) Halajnia, A.; Oustan, S.; Najafi, N.; Khataee, A. R.; Lakzian, A. Adsorption-Desorption Characteristics of Nitrate, Phosphate
589 and Sulfate on Mg-Al Layered Double Hydroxide. *Appl. Clay Sci.* **2013**, *80–81*, 305–312.
590 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2013.05.002>.
- 591 (49) Everaert, M.; Slenders, K.; Dox, K.; Smolders, S.; De Vos, D.; Smolders, E. The Isotopic Exchangeability of Phosphate in
592 Mg-Al Layered Double Hydroxides. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2018**, *520*, 25–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2018.03.010>.
- 593 (50) Liu, P.; Zhu, B.; Yuan, X.; Tong, G.; Su, Y.; Zhu, X. Physiochemical Properties and Bioapplication of Nano- and Microsized
594 Hydroxy Zinc Phosphate Particles Modulated by Reaction Temperature. *J. Mater. Chem. B* **2015**, *3* (7), 1301–1312.
595 <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4tb01049c>.
- 596 (51) Boonchom, B.; Baitahe, R.; Kongtaweelert, S.; Vittayakorn, N. Kinetics and Thermodynamics of Zinc Phosphate Hydrate
597 Synthesized by a Simple Route in Aqueous and Acetone Media. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2010**, *49* (8), 3571–3576.
598 <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie901626z>.

- 599 (52) Grzmil, B.; Kic, B.; Lubkowski, K. Studies on Obtaining of Zinc Phosphate Nanomaterials. *Rev. Adv. Mater. Sci.* **2007**, *14*
600 (1), 46–48.
- 601 (53) Singh, R.; Nye, P. H. The Effect of Soil PH and High Urea Concentrations on Urease Activity in Soil. *J. Soil Sci.* **1984**, *35* (4),
602 519–527. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2389.1984.tb00609.x>.
- 603 (54) Xie, R. J.; Mackenzie, A. F.; Lou, Z. J. Causal Modeling PH and Phosphate Effects on Molybdate Sorption in Three
604 Temperate Soils. *Soil Sci.* **1993**, *155* (6).
- 605 (55) Rebafka, F. P.; Ndunguru, B. J.; Marschner, H. Single Superphosphate Depresses Molybdenum Uptake and Limits Yield
606 Response to Phosphorus in Groundnut (*Arachis Hypogaea* L.) Grown on an Acid Sandy Soil in Niger, West Africa. *Fertil.*
607 *Res.* **1993**, *150* (2), 213–222. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00013018>.
- 608